

Sensity

stanza
www.stanza.co.uk
stanza@sublime.net

Stanza: Biographical information

Stanza is a London based British artist who specializes in net art, networked spaces, installations and performances. His award winning online projects have been invited for exhibition in digital festivals around the world, and Stanza also travels extensively to present his net art, lecturing and giving performances of his audiovisual interactions. His works explore artistic and technical opportunities to enable new aesthetic perspectives, experiences and perceptions within context of architecture, data spaces and online environments. www.stanza.co.uk

Description of Piece: Sensity.

I have set up a wireless sensor network around my house in London. I live nearby a railway line, a factory, some trees and a mobile phone mast. (This is using real data). This artwork captures this change to try to understand the underlying fabric of city space. Sensity is part of "The Emergent City" series of works by Stanza.

Sensity artworks are made from the data that is collected across the urban and environment infrastructure. A network of sensors, some fixed, and some embedded, collects data which is then published online. The sensors then interpret the micro-data of the interactive city. The output from the sensors displays the emotional state of the city online and the information will be used to create installations and sculptural artifacts. The sensor network can be moved from urban to rural setting and different types of visualization can be made depending on the environment. Sensity is an open social sculpture that informs the world and creates new meaningful experiences. By embedding the sensors we can re-engage with the urban fabric and enable new artistic metaphors within city space. The sensors are positioned across the city. Custom software enables these sensors to communicate with one another in a network. The data can be used to create visualizations in an open source environment. Online users can also re-interpret the data and interrogate the various sensors in the network as eventually this will all be open sourced as well.

The interactions of all this data, controlled via interfaces re-form and re-contextualize urban experiences in real time. <http://www.stanza.co.uk/sensity/index.html>. For the installation version please see the website. The piece needs a computer and projector.

